

FATE OF ¹⁵N UREA AS PLANT AVAILABLE FORM WITH AND WITHOUT BIOCHAR IN THE SOIL PROFILE (0-30CM)

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Abstract

Urea fertilizer is broadly used in agriculture sector because of higher water solubility and quick release into plant available nitrogen (N) but causes more N losses as leaching and gaseous emissions. However, different types of amendments have been applied to overcome this problem, but the byproduct of biomasses pyrolysis called biochar is getting fame because of its environmental benefits. This study is based upon the comparative analysis of urea fertilizer composed of stable isotopic nitrogen (¹⁵N) in lysimeters (30cm diameter and 35cm height) with (BT) and without biochar (CK) for *Brassica Camprestis Var. Chinensis* plantation in two successive cropping seasons (April to July and Sept. to December) in Beijing, China. The comparative analysis showed that plant yield was non-significant, but BT accumulative (first and second seasons) N plant uptake increased 10.62%, decreased N leaching 10.7%, retained more N in soil 11.37% and reduction in unaccounted losses 11.8% as compared to CK. Moreover, soil in BT showed non-significant increase in soil pH and decrease in bulk density but significant increase in EC after second season. Thus, biochar amendment in agricultural soil reduces the N losses and increases residence time for urea in soil.

1. Introduction

Nitrogenous fertilizers play an important role in modern agriculture for crop production, especially urea which is the most abundantly used fertilizer in the world because of its high nitrogen content (46%) and water solubility, low cost and ease of application (Azeem et al. 2014). Globally, agricultural practices with high nitrogen (N) fertilization and water availability (irrigation or rainfall) lead to N losses as surface runoff, leaching below root zone, volatilization or immobilization by microorganisms (Gu et al. 2016). Number of management strategies have been applied to control these losses but failed to achieve adequate N use efficiency. Unfortunately, these N losses are threatening to environment and increase the input expenditures of the farmers. Many studies reported that N losses from the agriculture sectors in China have been getting the headway environmental issue because farmers are adding N fertilizer surplus from the requirements (Ti et al. 2015). In fact, the crop yield is not proportion with the N fertilizer above the crop requirements (Fan et al. 2007). According to Wang and Zhou (2014), the efficient use of N fertilizer depends upon the timing, rate, source and placement of N fertilizer.

Once urea is incorporated into the agriculture soil, N-transformation gets the start which is a complex process and depends upon the soil characteristics (porosity, permeability, dispersion coefficients, absorption, and biomasses). However, urea incorporated in soil will be distributed into plant available forms (nitrate and ammonium ions), unaccounted forms (gaseous state emission) and organic forms trapped into biomasses which further decompose to plant available forms after mineralization

(Ding et al. 2015). As the fate of urea can be analyzed by the ^{15}N tracer technique and N balance equation such as determined the amount of ^{15}N taken by plant, remaining in soil and leached down as nitrate ($\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$) and ammonium ($\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$) ions (Zhang et al. 2010). The amount of urea applied to soil for crop production might be entrapped into biomasses and available to upcoming crops. Thus, N fertilization in one season may be retained in the soil and will be available to the next cropping season (Ferchaud et al. 2016). As plants consume N in $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ and $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ forms, so N trapped into biomasses (microbial masses, plant residues or organic matters) or retained in the soil, will be available after mineralization.

This study was conducted to analyze the fate of ^{15}N urea as plant available nitrogen (Nitrate and ammonium) and total nitrogen in the soil-plant system. The experiment based on the analysis of soil filled columns (lysimeters) treated with (BT) and without biochar (CK) for the two successive cropping of *Brassica Compestris Var. Chinensis* which has higher nutritional values and extensively planted in China with an abundance of N fertilization (Li and Wang. 2007). The ^{15}N tracer technique was used to distinguish the plant N from fertilizer, soil N and the N fluxes in the soil-plant system (Jia et al. 2011) during the cropping seasons. Biochar, the end product of biomass pyrolysis or incomplete combustion, was incorporated which has been considered as a beneficial soil amendment that can enhance carbon storage, agricultural productivities and prevent nutrient transport below the root zone (Woolf et al. 2010, Laird et al. 2010).

The purpose of the study was to compare the fate of ^{15}N urea in the presence and

absence of biochar such as measure the differences in crop N uptake, mineral N (nitrate and ammonium) leaching, N retained in soil, soil pH, soil EC, crop yield and total N obtained during and after two successive cropping in the lysimeters.

2. Materials and Methods

Experiment Details:

This experiment was conducted in a greenhouse of the Institute of Environment and Sustainable Development in Agriculture, CAAS Beijing China. Six soil filled lysimeters (Diameter 30cm and height 35cm) with leachate collection assembly were designed to plant *Brassica Compestris Var. Chinensis* for the successive two cropping seasons (April to July and September to December). The weight of every single lysimeter was 33kg and filled upto 32cm same for both treatments. The soil (45.9% sand, 36.9% silt and 17.2% clay) was collected from the Shunyi District, having initial soil properties such as 1.46g/cm³ bulk density, 1.07g N/kg total nitrogen, 8.15 pH and 11.5mS/m (115μS/cm) EC.

Experiment Procedure: All six lysimeters were filled with well-graded soil and biochar was applied in three lysimeters with the rate of 20ton/ha. Fertilization (N: P: K:300:150:300 respectively) in the form of SSP, Potassium Sulphate and 98.5% enriched ¹⁵N urea (in water solution) were given to all lysimeters prior to plantation (15 plants in each lysimeter). Surface irrigation was scheduled as 5.08 cm per week in both cropping seasons. Plant dry matter was made as one month after plantation and two weeks thereafter up to the last harvest. Thus, 10 dry matters (plant extracts) were prepared in the two-cropping season for every treatment. In the next cropping season, poultry manure compost (150N kg/ha) was given

as fertilizer to all six lysimeters before plantation. Soil tests pH, EC, total nitrogen, nitrate and ammonium were made prior to fertilization, after the first and second harvest. Leachate volume was recorded and processed for the analysis of ammonium and nitrate (¹⁴N and ¹⁵N). Thus, two treatments; biochar (BT) and without biochar (CK) with three repetitions were tested for the fate of ¹⁵N in two successive cropping seasons of *Brassica Campestris Var. Chinensis*. The ¹⁵N labeled concentration (Ndff) in soil, plant and leachate was calculated by the isotopic dilution principle (Hauck and Bremner, 1976) as,

$$\%Ndff = \frac{(\text{Atom } \%^{15}\text{N excess in soil or plant or leachate})}{(\text{Atom } \%^{15}\text{N excess in fertilizer added})} \times 100$$

$$Ndff \text{ (mg)}$$

$$= \left(\% \frac{Ndff}{100} \right)$$

$$\times (\text{Total N in soil, or plant or leachate})$$

$$\text{Total } 15\text{N applied in Urea}$$

$$= 15\text{N in plant extract}$$

$$+ 15\text{N in leachate} + 15\text{N in soil}$$

$$+ 15\text{N volatilized (emitted as ammonia or N oxide gases)}$$

$$\text{Total } 15\text{N applied in fertilizer} = (15\text{N plant uptake} + 15\text{N leached} + 15\text{N retained in Soil} + 15\text{N unaccounted losses})$$

Unaccounted losses covered all the gaseous emission in the form of volatilization or nitrogen oxides or elemental nitrogen of ¹⁵N as well as the losses excluding from the plant uptake, leaching and retained in lysimeter soil.

Laboratory Analysis: Nitrate and ammonium analysis were made with the help of Lachat flow injection (FIA) instrument designed by Růžička and Hansen (1978). For nitrate and ammonium analysis KCl 2M solution with soil (1:5) was prepared in a lab, whereas leachate was directly used in FIA instrument after filtration.

Samples were prepared for soil and leachate to analyze the concentration of ^{15}N nitrate and ^{15}N ammonium as guided by Coplen et al. (2007) and Goerges and Dittert (1998) respectively. Plant extract was prepared as plants unplugged from roots, wash (in de-ionized water), oven dried 70°C for 24 hours, crushed and tested for ^{14}N and ^{15}N nitrogen. However, all the isotopic tests were conducted by the Isoprime 100IRMS United Kingdom. Air-dried soil (graded from 2mm sieve) and de-ionized water in ratio 1:5 was mechanical shake (15rpm for an hour) to make a solution for the soil pH and EC testing (Rayment et al. 1992). Digital EC meter was calibrated in solution 141.3mS/m at 25°C and pH meter in buffer solution pH 4, 6 and 7, and then used for measurements in such a way that electrodes were washed prior and after each reading.

2.1 Statistical Analysis

Single way ANOVA with F and T-tests were performed to analyze the significant variations between the initial values (Before fertilization) and values after first cropping season and final values recorded after the second harvest for soil pH, EC, bulk density and total mineral nitrogen. Percentage comparison between treatments for the yield, total ^{15}N uptake, total N leaching and total ^{15}N retained after two cropping seasons were made by MS Office Excel and GraphPad Prism with SEM (Standard Error of Mean) analysis and graph designing.

3. Results and Discussion:

3.1. ^{15}N Recovery in Dry Matter

Total 10 dry matter (DM) were prepared in two successive cropping. Accumulative mean ^{15}N recoveries in BT and CK were 38.42% and 27.7% such as 80.26% and 81.2% uptake in first cropping season respectively. Hence, most of ^{15}N recoveries occurred in first cropping season for both treatments but overall BT

had utilized higher tracer as compared to CK as shown in figure-1. Biochar addition may influence soil mineralization, water holding capacity, root architecture, plant ecophysiology, nutrient supply, microbial forms and function (Clough et al. 2013). According to Saarnio et al. (2013) biochar increased plant N uptake which might be the reason that plants in BT absorbed more ^{15}N in both cropping seasons. As biochar may increase $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ concentration in soil (Nelson et al. 2011) because of decrease in N mineralization rate (Dempster et al. 2012), reduction in ammonia volatilization (Steiner et al. 2010), increment in nitrate sorption (Yao et al. 2012) and function as ammonia sink (Doydora et al. 2011, Luo et al. 2016). Moreover, BT exhibited more N uptake efficiency as compared to CK but overall, 38.42% efficiency in two cropping season was not economical or environmental safe mode of fertilization in China which is already under worse conditions of greenhouse gases (GHG) emission and nitrate leaching. Cameron et al. (2013) analyzed that worldwide vegetable crops had lower N fertilizer efficiencies as compared to cereal and other crops because of a shallow rooting system and higher fertilization. As *Brassica Camprestis Var. Chinensis* is vegetable crop with a shallow root depth and architecture. Thereby, it might be the reason of lower N efficiencies in both treatments.

3.2. ^{15}N in Leachate

A total 9 leachate samples were collected during two cropping seasons. Mean ^{15}N leached down from BT and CK lysimeters were 8.06% and 18.75% of the total applied ^{15}N . Tracer concentrations were found in all leachates that clarify the lasting trend of applied urea in soil medium as maximum ^{15}N in first four leachates and declined thereafter up to

the end as shown in figure-2. Moreover, BT leachates carried more ammonium concentration, about 14% of the total mineral N as compared to CK having 5%. Many studies revealed that biochar addition decrease inorganic N leaching (Sika et al. 2014, Yao et al. 2012) and lower N mineralization rate (Luo et al. 2016, Tambone and Adani. 2016) which might be the reason of lower N leaching and higher ammonium ion in BT treatments. Urea mineralization to peak level of inorganic forms (plant available nitrogen) during incubation or field condition was reported different but in most of studies peak N concentration developed after 25-30 days and decreased to non-significant level after 125 days (Luo et al. 2016) which is supporting the trend of N leaching in this study.

3.3. ^{15}N in Soil

Different processes like ^{15}N urea mineralization, crop uptake, volatilization and leaching decreased to ^{15}N levels in BT and CK soils as 59.5% and 35.28% after the first cropping and thereafter, 31.518% and 20.15% at the end of second cropping respectively, as shown in figure 3. Moreover, BT treatment had 1.69 times total ^{15}N retained in soil after first cropping season and 1.56 times after the second cropping season as compared to CK. Many researchers found that biochar reduced the N mineralization (Baiga and Rao, 2017, Luo et al. 2016) which might be increased the urea lasting time in soil as happened in our study.

3.4. Soil properties

It was observed that only electrical conductivity (EC) was significantly changed in BT treatment but the rest of other properties such as soil pH, and bulk densities were not significantly varied after two successive cropping seasons as shown in table-1. Biochar has porous structure with large surface area and capable of changing soil bulk density,

pH, total nitrogen and total carbon once added in agriculture soil (Chen et al., 2014) whereas, the resilient nature of soil brings these changes back to the initial stage within 1-3 years (Quilliam et al. 2012). Many studies analyzed that biochar induced the soil EC (Nigussie et al. 2012, Zhang et al. 2016) which supported our findings in this study.

3.5. ^{15}N balance

It was observed that BT aggravated more plant uptake, less N leaching (nitrate and ammonium) and less unaccounted losses with higher N retained in soil as shown in figure-4. Unaccounted losses measured for BT and CK were larger, about 33.4% and 21.6% of applied N respectively. These limits crossed the Chen et al. (2014) observation that gaseous emission losses of N fertilizer occurred 21-30% in China. When urea fertilizer was incorporated, gaseous N emission losses as ammonia was observed much more than nitrogen oxides (Asing et al. 2008) and biochar had an ability to absorb ammonia emitting after soil fertilization (Taghizadeh-Toosi et al. 2012). These might be the reasons for less unaccounted losses in BT than CK. Few researchers such as David (2015) reported a significant increase in crop yield after biochar amendment in soil but in this study slightly increment (not significant) in yield was found in BT. However, the total N percentage in plant dry matter was nearly 3.5-5.5% same in both treatments.

According to our finding, biochar composed of poultry and straw at 650°C pyrolysis has the ability to retain and extend the residence time of urea applied N which might be utilized by forthcoming cropping, decrease N leaching, increase soil electrical conductivity and reduce unaccounted losses but not reasonable effects on soil pH, soil bulk density and total yield of

the *Brassica Camprestis Var. Chinensis* plantation in lysimeter after the 2 successive cropping seasons. Therefore, biochar formation is an environmentally safe procedure to convert biological waste into amendment that may help to enhance soil fertility. Unaccounted N losses (urea volatilization) were not separately measured, so further investigation is suggested.

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Figure 1. Total nitrogen with standard error in mean (SEM) in dry matter of biochar added (BT) and without biochar added (CK) treatments

Figure 2. Total mineral ¹⁵N with standard error in mean (SEM) in the leachates collected during the two cropping seasons from Biochar added (BT) and without Biochar (CK) treated lysimeters

Figure 3. Decreasing total ¹⁵N concentration (%) in the lysimeters soils after the first and the second cropping for Biochar added (BT) and without Biochar (CK) treatments

■ Leachate ■ Plant Uptake ■ Soil ■ Unaccount Losses

Figure 4. Total ^{15}N distribution after the two successive cropping season for Biochar added (BT) and without Biochar (CK) treatments

Table-1: Parameters mean variation from initial values after first and second cropping season in the lysimeter soil

Soil Properties	Treatments	Initial values	After 1st Cropping	After 2nd Cropping
pH	BT	8.01 ± 0.3	8.07 ± .30	8.10 ± .35
	CK	8.09 ± 0.4	8.03 ± .38	8.01 ± .40
EC (mS/m)	BT	85 ± 25	255 ± 100 *	295 ± 115*
	CK	90 ± 25	105 ± 35	99 ± 25
Bulk Density (gm/cm ³)	BT	145 ± 2.5	148 ± 3.5	148.5 ± 3.5
	CK	143 ± 3.5	142 ± 3.5	143.5 ± 3.5
Total Nitrogen in soil (g N/kg)	CK	1.074	1.095±.04	1.081±0.5
	BT	1.079	1.092±0.7	1.084±0.6
Yield (ton/ha)	CK	-	10.763 ±1.0	8.892±0.85
	BT	-	9.989±1.55	8.543±0.75

* indicates the significant difference

Figure Captions:

Figure 1: Total ^{15}N in plant extracts for biochar added (BT) and without biochar added (CK) treatments

Figure 2: Total mineral ^{15}N with standard error in mean (SEM) in the leachates collected during the two cropping seasons from Biochar added (BT) and without Biochar (CK) treated lysimeters

Figure 3: Decreasing total ^{15}N (%) concentration in the lysimeters soils after the first and the second cropping for Biochar added (BT) and without Biochar (CK) treatments

Figure 4: Total ^{15}N distribution in lysimeter soil after the first and the second cropping for Biochar added (BT) and without Biochar (CK) treatments

Table Captions:

Table-1: Soil properties variation from initial values after first and second cropping season in the lysimeter soil